

**CHANGES IN THE INFRASTRUCTURE OF UZBEKISTAN AND ITS
SOUTHERN REGIONS DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE****Yakitjan Buvabaevna Kadirova****TSPU named after Nizami, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)**

Abstract: In this article, it is written that since the first days of our independence, it has been written that the restoration of the enormous, priceless spiritual and cultural heritage created by our ancestors over many centuries has become an extremely important task that has risen to the level of state policy. The cultural values and spiritual heritage of the people have served as a powerful source of spirituality for the peoples of the East for thousands of years. It is stated that despite the long-lasting severe ideological pressure, the people of Uzbekistan have managed to preserve their historical and cultural values and unique traditions that have been passed down from generation to generation.

Introduction: In honor of the independence of Uzbekistan, a lot of work has been done in our country. If we look at it from this point of view, architecture has been freed from the shackles of previous restrictions, the reins of habit have been cut off. The state monopoly over architecture has partially lost its power, especially in private housing construction, a new level of quality and speed has risen rapidly. The cities of Uzbekistan, especially the capital Tashkent, have changed a lot in terms of architecture in a short period of time, turning into a beautiful, prosperous, lush garden city that meets modern requirements. Oliy Majlis, Oksaroy Residence, Tashkent Government, Turkestan Palace, National Bank, Intercontinental, and Central Hotel are among the magnificent buildings of the independence period. The building of the Uzbek National Academic Drama Theater was renovated in a very magnificent quality, a magnificent new building was built for the Uzbek Conservatory, and the Museum of the Timurids was established. maritime measures have been implemented. In particular, on the occasion of the 1225th anniversary of the birth of Imam Bukhari, the restoration of a huge architectural complex (mausoleum, mosque, architectural office, library and kitchen) in the village of Khartang, Samarkand region, on the basis of a new project (1998), was greatly appreciated and applauded in the Muslim world. was greeted with On the occasion of the 1200th anniversary of Ahmad al-Farghani, a statue and a park were built in the cities of Quva and Ferghana. In Samarkand, an

architectural monument was restored over the grave of Imam Moturidi, and an architectural complex dedicated to the memory of Burhoniddin Marginani was built in the city of Margilon. An architectural museum-garden dedicated to the memory of the victims of repression was established in Tashkent, which became a sacred shrine "Memorial of Martyrs".[1]

In the dramaturgy of the period of independence, special attention was paid to the creation of the image of statesmen such as Amir Temur, Babur, as well as Ulugbek and Jalaluddin Manguberdi, who played a major role in the historical destiny of the Uzbek people, but were condemned in the Soviet era. Alpomish, Ahmad al-Farghani, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, Mirza Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, whose jubilees were celebrated internationally, were erected statues and created paintings dedicated to them. Exquisite icon painting, calligraphy and book illustration were restored. In particular, as a result of the celebration of Kamoliddin Behzod's jubilee, great attention to this field, a group of miniatures, painters and calligraphers appeared in the republic. H. Soliyev's calligraphic works were recognized internationally. The State Prize named after Kamoliddin Behzod was established, T. Boltaboyev, H. Nazirov, G. Kamolov became its first owners.

In 1999, the first Islamic University in Central Asia was opened in Tashkent. There are 10 religious educational institutions, including the Tashkent Islamic Institute, and 9 secondary special educational institutions operating in our country. Two of them are women's educational institutions.

the spiritual sphere has become more evident especially in the last three years. Acting President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Prime Minister Sh. Mirziyoyev, speaking at the opening ceremony of the 43rd session of the Council of Foreign Ministers of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation on October 16, 2016, said that the theme of the conference was "Education and enlightenment - towards peace and creativity." The slogan "1" clearly expresses our priority directions. Also, the head of Uzbekistan said, "In the great history, nothing goes without a trace. It is preserved in the blood and historical memory of the people and is manifested in practical work. That is why he is powerful. Preservation of historical heritage, learning and passing it on from generation to generation is one of the most important priority directions of our state's policy. This is extremely important in the conditions of globalization, in which new threats, including the danger of "mass culture" and the mood of gentrification, are emerging, and the danger of the loss of morals and values is emerging. [2]

Methods Methodological foundations. The attitude towards religious values has changed radically. The use of religious values in the path of knowledge and enlightenment, in the path of education of the young generation, began to bear fruit. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, has always stressed the need for a unique approach to religious values, that is, a deep understanding of the incomparable place in the future of our nation and the education of our youth. For example, "It is the honorable duty of each of us to preserve and value our sacred religion, which embodies our ancient values and moral qualities. Islam means understanding the truth, it encourages people to do good deeds, calls each of us to goodness and peace, teaches to be a real person." A research center named after Imam Bukhari has been established in Samarkand, and an Islamic civilization center has been established in Tashkent. The purpose of this is to inculcate the real humanitarian essence of Islam, enlightened Islam into the minds of our children. In this way, they will come to these places and get the necessary and most important knowledge and ideas about what great things our great ancestors did. Most importantly, the sense of pride in our rich history and cultural heritage grows in their hearts (speech delivered at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 25th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, December 7, 2017). Also, the work of establishing scientific and educational institutions such as scientific research centers and Islamic Academy named after Imam Termizi has started. The establishment of the Center of Islamic Civilization in the city of Tashkent gave an opportunity to fight under the slogan "Enlightenment against oppression". Therefore, on the initiative of the President, schools of hadith studies were established in Samarkand at the Imam Bukhari Scientific Center, schools of theology at the Imam Motrudi Center, schools of Islamic Law at the Margilani Center in Fergana, Sufism at the Bahauddin Naqshband Center in Bukhara, and schools of Aqeedah at the Abu Muin Nasafi Center in Kashkadarya. [3]

In Uzbekistan, placing national literature and the best examples of world literature on social networks and their wide promotion has risen to the level of state policy. Reading has been widely promoted among our people, especially among our youth. In this, new, effective methods and financial incentives were effectively used. Fortunately, among the youth of our nation, who are hungry for knowledge, a young generation has been formed who have read and analyzed hundreds of artistic and historical works, memorized thousands of verses of poems and are using them for the spiritual development of our people. The respect for the poet, writer, and scientist was a huge breakthrough in this field. Our President Sh.Mirziyoyev explains the state policy in

this area as follows: "The issue of constant care of creative intellectuals who are engineers of the human heart, who have devoted their unique talent and skills to raising the spirituality of our people, is a special issue in our program in takes over".

Support for the activities of creative organizations, artistic associations, strengthening of their material and technical base, infrastructure networks has been further strengthened. Special attention was paid to materially and morally stimulating young people entering the world of culture, art, literature and press, and improving their housing conditions. In the greenest corner of the National Park of Uzbekistan, Adiblar Avenue, the building of the Writers' Union was built. The House of Artists was built and commissioned.

The nationalism, humanitarianism, balance of the social justice criteria of the reforms carried out in the country depend on the effectiveness of the state policy on the treatment of women in the society and their application. In 2017, there were 514 doctors of science, 6 academicians, 15 Heroes of Uzbekistan, 17 senators, 154 deputies of the Legislative Chamber, and more than 23 percent of local council deputies were women. Dozens of our women have received high honorary titles of our state, such as "Scientist of Uzbekistan", "People's poet of Uzbekistan", "People's teacher of Uzbekistan", "People's artist of Uzbekistan ". Among them, 240 young talents were awarded the "Zulfiya" State Award. [3]

In this field, it is necessary to emphasize the excellent services of non-governmental non-commercial organizations in Uzbekistan. For example, by the "Union of Women Scientists" of Uzbekistan, the development of scientific research among our women, the realization of innovative ideas from scientific research, the publication of scientific results, especially the organization of various competitions among young researchers, has been doing good deeds such as rewarding the winners.

On February 3, 2017, during the visit of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the National Park of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, the construction of the Adiblar Avenue complex was announced. On April 18 of this year, the relevant decision of the head of our state was adopted, the architectural and conceptual project of the avenue was developed, and in the territory of the National Park in the city of Tashkent, on an area of more than 8 hectares, Babur, Ogahi, Berdaq, Muqimi, Furqat, Behbudi, Avloni, Cholpon, Kadiri, Tolepbergen Qayipbergenov, Ibrayim Yusupov, Aleksandr Feinberg, etc., was built along the Adiblar Avenue with new memorial complexes. Around the magnificent statue of our Grandfather Navoi, a

complete architectural ensemble was created based on the architectural and artistic composition of the statues of more than 20 famous poets and writers. Also, the new building of the Writers' Union was built here. Creative schools named after our great writers were established in Karaka province and in a number of our regions. Also, the regional theaters of Ko'kan city, Jizzakh and Khorezm were reconstructed. The Fergana regional branch of the State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan was established.

The social reforms carried out in recent years in our country are taking a special path towards spiritual prosperity. The speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev at the meeting with creative intellectuals on August 3, 2017 is important in understanding the state policy and the spirit of the times. The speeches of the head of our country were based on recognition of achievements in this regard and, therefore, deep analysis of problems in the field. After all, it has been confirmed for centuries that spiritual development is the development of the country and nation.

Open dialogue, objective and critical improvement of the development processes of our culture and art, the meeting held in the tone of comprehensive thinking about the problems served to find solutions to many issues. Addressing the creative intellectuals, the President said: "Of course, we always gratefully acknowledge the great merits of cultural representatives in the spiritual development of our people. But let's put our hands on our chests and say honestly: does today's activity of our creative intellectuals satisfy our society, first of all, you, who always live and burn for the fate of the country, are satisfied?"

I think that you yourself feel that nowadays there is a lack of the spirit of living with new creative ideas and initiatives in the spirit of culture and art." While presenting these points, we must deeply understand that today all citizens are equally concerned with the development of the country, that indifference and indifference are the most relevant habits of today, and that social activity is an important factor for stable participation in today's rapid international processes. At the meeting, important tasks were set for literature, art, mass media and various aspects of spirituality in the period when Uzbekistan is becoming a huge construction and creative place. One of the biggest spiritual events in Uzbekistan is the music festival "Sharq taronalari", which has been held since 1997. In 1997, 57 artists from 31 countries took part in this music festival, which is unique and a true celebration of art with its unique spirit, and in 2018, 241 talented singers and musicians from 58 countries participated.

The "History of Uzbekistan" channel was launched as part of the National Television and Radio Company of Uzbekistan in order to inculcate the priceless legacy of our great scholars and writers, our saints, the invincible sarkanda and the courage of our figures into the minds of young people, and to strengthen their feelings of national pride and pride .

On March 14, 2000 Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the establishment of the honorary title "People's Bakhshi" "In order to encourage the citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan for their significant contributions in education, in making our people, especially the youth, enjoy the riches of our many-thousand-year-old culture and glorifying the independence and glory of the Motherland with their creative and executive activities" The honorary title of "People's Charity of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was established. [4]

Also, on April 5-10, 2019, an international festival of the art of giving was held in the city of Termiz. Bakhsh school was newly established in the city of Termiz. Hundreds of our young people are learning folk art in the music and art schools of the republic. A 100-story "Monuments of Uzbek folk creativity " is being published in Uzbekistan.

To sum up restoring the huge, priceless spiritual and cultural heritage created by our ancestors over many centuries from the first days of our independence has become an extremely important task that has risen to the level of state policy. Indeed, the broad development of the spiritual sphere, which is one of the roots of the social sphere in Uzbekistan, took place in the eyes of our people, with their active participation. It is recognized by the people of the world that our people treat their history, traditions, national and religious values with special respect. Also, in the conditions of market relations, paying great attention to spirituality and enlightenment work is one of the unique features of the appearance of a new society in independent Uzbekistan.

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